

Role of auxiliary donors in tuning the selectivity of C-H activation in arylazonaphthalenes by palladium(II) : Isolation and photoisomerization of isomeric cyclopalladates[†]

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Abstract : Selective activation of C2(naphthyl)-H and C8(naphthyl)-H bonds in a group of substrates having a diazene function as primary donor along with thioether or sulfinyl groups as auxiliary donors has been achieved by palladium(II) at room temperature. The selectivity of C(naphthyl)-H activation in the diazene substrates has been shown to be controlled by the presence of acidic or basic additives. At room temperature, regiospecific C2(naphthyl)-H has been achieved in presence of Et₃N, leading to the formation of *ortho*-palladate. On the other hand, regiospecific activation of C8(naphthyl)-H resulted in presence of acetic acid affording *peri*-palladate. The solid-state structures of the representative cyclopalladates have been determined by single crystal X-ray diffraction method. Both the *ortho*-palladates and *peri*-palladates contain five-membered carbopalladacycles [C,N], whereas the [N,S] chelate rings are five-membered in the *ortho*-isomers and six-membered in *peri*-isomers. The photochemical transformation of the *peri*-palladates into the *ortho*-palladates i.e. C8(naphthyl)-Pd → C2(naphthyl)-Pd has been achieved.

Keywords : C-H activation, palladium, cyclopallation, isomerism.

Introduction

C-H bond activation has been an active area in the domain of chemical research for the past few decades¹. One of the mildest ways to achieve selective functionalization of C-H bonds in organic molecules is cyclometallation reaction². Using this route, selective activation of a particular C-H bond within a complex molecule is achieved by introducing a coordinating group (primary donor) at a suitable position within the substrate, which ultimately leads to the formation of metal-carbon bond³. However, several organic molecules having primary donor at a given position may possess more than one non-equivalent C-H bonds as potential metallation sites. Therefore, selective activation of one of the target C-H bonds in these molecules is a challenging task.

For the past decade or so, we have been active in selective activation of non-equivalent C(naphthyl)-H bonds of naphthylazoarenes (Scheme 1)⁴. The naphthyl moiety with diazene function⁵ at C1 can offer the C2 (I) or C8 (II) positions for metallation (Scheme 2). Recently, we have explored how the non-equivalent C(naphthyl)-H bonds can be selectively activated by palladium(II) at room temperature with incorporation of different auxiliary donors along with variation of the position of primary donor. In presence of the hydroxyl auxiliary donor at the 2'-position of naphthylazoarenes, both C2(naphthyl)-H and C8(naphthyl)-H activation have been realized. Moreover, exclusive activation of C2(naphthyl)-H bond by palladium(II) has been achieved with the change of auxiliary -OH (naphtholato) donor by neutral alkoxy group^{4a}.

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

	Ar	R'	Ref
HL1		H	4
HL2		H	4
HL3		OMe	This work
HL3'		OMe	This work
HL4		OMe	This work
HL4'		OMe	This work

Scheme 1. Naphthylazoarenes used in the study.

Scheme 2. Non-equivalent C(naphthyl)-H bonds for metal chelation.

In continuation of our earlier study, herein we have explored the role of alkylthioethers (-SR) and alkylsulfinyls (-S(O)R) as auxiliary donor towards selective activation of C(naphthyl)-H bond activation of naphthylazoarenes by palladium. Attempts have been made to tune the reaction condition to achieve selective C(naphthyl)-H activation at room temperature. The isolation, characterization and structural aspects of the cyclopalladates have been discussed. Moreover, visible light-induced isomerization of cyclopalladates has also been described.

Experimental

Materials and instruments :

Palladium dichloride was purchased from Arora Matthey (Kolkata, India). 2-Aminothiophenol (SD Fine Chemicals, India), methyl iodide, ethyl iodide and benzyl chloride (SD Fine Chemicals, India) were used without further purification. The diazene substrates (HL3 and HL4) were prepared following the reported method^{4d,6} whereas HL3' and HL4' were obtained by oxidizing HL3 and HL4

by H₂O₂ in glacial acetic acid at low temperature⁷. Visible and Ultraviolet spectra were recorded on a JASCO V530 spectrophotometer equipped with thermostated cell holder. Infrared spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-500 and Shimadzu FTIR8300. ¹H NMR data were collected in CDCl₃ solvent by using a Bruker DPX 300 NMR spectrometer. Elemental microanalyses (C, H and N) were done by either Perkin-Elmer (Model 240C) or Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer.

Isolation of the cyclopalladates :

Isolation of 3a and 3b :

An ethanolic solution (10 cm³) of HL³ (0.04 g, 0.11 mmol) was slowly added to sodium tetrachloropalladate (0.035 g, 0.12 mmol) in ethanol (10 cm³). Immediately the colour of the mixture changed to pink violet and the mixture was stirred for 2 h at 300 K. The mixture was kept for 24 h at room temperature. The solvent was removed by evaporation and the residue was thoroughly washed with water followed by a mixture of ethanol and water (1 : 1, v/v). The residue was dried and dissolved in dichloromethane. The mixture was chromatographed on thin layer of silica gel in preparative scale, a blue band containing (3a) followed by a pink band of (3b) were separated by 10% methanol in benzene (v/v). The separation step was repeated twice. Yield : 3a, 0.015 g, 0.0285 mmol, ca. 25% and 3b, 0.025 g, 0.0476 mmol, ca. 40%.

3a : UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂), λ/nm (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) : 622^{sh} (8700), 595 (10500), 420^{sh} (5300), 378 (5900), 305 (16700), 245 (26200), 230 (28400); IR (KBr; v/cm⁻¹) : 1458 (-N=N-); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; standard SiMe₄) : δ 4.25 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.67 (3H, s, -SCH₃), 7.0-9.0 (9H, m, aromatic).

3b : UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂), λ/nm (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) : 525 (15100), 500 (11900), 365^{sh} (6500), 298 (10300), 235 (21800); IR (KBr; v/cm⁻¹) : 1456 (-N=N-); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; standard SiMe₄) : δ 4.21 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.65 (3H, s, -SCH₃), 7.0-9.0 (9H, m, aromatic).

Isolation of 4a and 4b :

Compounds 4a and 4b were prepared by above mentioned process using 2-benzylthiophenylazo-4-methoxy-1-naphthalene. Yield : 4a, 0.011 g, 0.0215 mmol, ca. 20% and 4b, 0.008 g, 0.0156 mmol, ca. 15%.

4a : UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂), λ/nm (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) :

620^{sh} (9400), 595 (11300), 420^{sh} (5600), 375 (6300), 305 (17600), 242 (28100), 228 (30300); IR (KBr; ν/cm^{-1}) : 1460 (-N=N-); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; standard SiMe₄) : δ 4.25 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 4.39 (3H, s, -SCH₂), 7.1–8.5 (9H, m, aromatic).

4b : UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂), λ/nm ($\epsilon/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 525 (20600), 500 (16600), 365^{sh} (8300), 298 (12400), 235 (28300); IR (KBr; ν/cm^{-1}) : 1446 (-N=N-); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; standard SiMe₄) : δ 4.20 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 4.48 (3H, s, -SCH₂), 7.1–8.5 (9H, m, aromatic).

Isolation of 3a' and 3b' :

3a' : UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂), λ/nm ($\epsilon/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 303 (18400), 411^{sh} (7200), 588 (15100), 616^{sh} (13400); IR (KBr; ν/cm^{-1}) : 1103 (S=O), 1462 (-N=N-); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; standard SiMe₄) : δ 4.234 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.64 (3H, s, -SCH₃), 7.0–9.034 (9H, m, aromatic).

3b' : UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂), λ/nm ($\epsilon/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 300 (11000), 358^{sh} (7900), 509 (16400), 533 (18800); IR (KBr; ν/cm^{-1}) : 1107 (S=O), 1463 (-N=N-); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; standard SiMe₄) : δ 4.26 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.464 (3H, s, -SCH₃), 7.0–9.055 (9H, m, aromatic).

Isolation of 4a' and 4b' :

4a' : UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂), λ/nm ($\epsilon/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 305 (22400), 412^{sh} (8400), 586 (19300), 615^{sh} (16800); IR (KBr; ν/cm^{-1}) : 1103 (S=O), 1458 (-N=N-); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; standard SiMe₄) : δ 4.26 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.67 (2H, m, -CH₂), 7.12–8.22 (14H, m, aromatic).

4b' : UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂), λ/nm ($\epsilon/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 299 (12000), 358^{sh} (8400), 509 (16700), 533 (19400); IR (KBr; ν/cm^{-1}) : 1100 (S=O), 1460 (-N=N-); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃; standard SiMe₄) : δ 4.187 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.64 (2H, m, -CH₂), 7.26–8.53 (14H, m, aromatic).

Cyclopalladation reactions in presence of triethylamine :

In a typical reaction, a stirred solution of 10 cm³ sodium tetrachloropalladate (0.035 g, 0.12 mmol) in ethanol (10 cm³) at 313 K was quickly added to a warm methanolic solution (40 cm³) of the diazene (0.11 mmol) at 313 K with 5–7 drops of triethylamine in it. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 20 min. The colour

of the solution changed to deep blue. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was washed with water followed by a mixture of ethanol and water (1 : 1, v/v). It was dried and further washed with small portions (5 cm³) of diethyl ether three times. The blue residue obtained was further purified by chromatography on a thin layer of silica gel in preparative scale. A blue band containing the *ortho*-palladate was separated by 10% acetonitrile in benzene (v/v).

Cyclopalladation reactions in presence of acetic acid :

A stirred solution of 10 ml sodium tetrachloropalladate (0.035 g, 0.12 mmol) in ethanol (10 cm³) at 288 K was quickly added to a methanolic solution (40 cm³) of the diazene substrate (0.11 mmol) at 288 K with 5–7 drops of glacial acetic acid in it. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 30 min. The colour of the solution changed to deep red. The solvent was then evaporated *in vacuo* and the residue was washed with water followed by a mixture of ethanol and water (1 : 1, v/v). It was dried and further washed with small portions (5 cm³) of diethyl ether three times. The red residue obtained was further purified by chromatography on a thin layer of silica gel in preparative scale. A reddish pink band containing the *peri*-palladate was separated by 10% acetonitrile in benzene (v/v).

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystal X-ray diffraction data collection were performed by mounting the suitable crystal on a glass thin fiber and transferring on to a Bruker SMART 1000 CCD area-detector diffractometer with normal focus fitted with a 2.4 kW sealed tube X-ray source (MoK α radiation, $\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) operating at 50 kV and 40 mA. The structure was solved by direct methods using SHELXS-97⁸ incorporated in WinGX crystallographic collective package⁹. All the hydrogen positions for the compound were initially located in the difference Fourier map, and for the final refinement, the hydrogen atoms were placed geometrically placed in the riding mode. The last cycles of refinement included atomic positions for all the atoms, anisotropic thermal parameters for all non-hydrogen atoms and isotropic thermal parameters for all the hydrogen atoms. Full-matrix-least-squares structure refinement against $|F^2|$ was carried out using SHELXL-97⁷. Molecular geometry calculations were performed with

PLATON¹⁰ and molecular graphics were prepared using ORTEP-3¹¹.

CCDC-1433664-1433666 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

Results and discussion

Cyclopalladation via C-H bond activation :

Disodium tetrachloropalladate(II), Na₂[PdCl₄] smoothly reacts with 2'-alkylthiophenylazo-1-naphthalenes (HL3 and HL4, Scheme 1) at room temperature in methanol and produces a violet color solution, which slowly precipitates a dark violet mass of a mixture of isomeric palladium cyclometallates (**3a** and **3b**) and (**4a** and **4b**) respectively (Scheme 3). The isomers have been separated using preparative thin layer chromatography on silica gel plates and characterized by elemental analysis and ¹H NMR. In ¹H NMR spectra the signals for -OMe and -SCH₂- groups of cyclopalladate (**4a**) appear at δ 4.25 and 4.39 respectively. For the corresponding *peri*-isomer (**4b**), the ¹H NMR signals of the -OMe and -SCH₂- groups appear at δ 4.19 and 4.47 respectively. The signals for aromatic protons of the cyclopalladates appear as complex pattern in the region δ 7.0–9.0 with correct integration ratio. In the ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectra of (**4a**) and (**4b**), the signals for palladated carbon appear at δ 224.21 and 209.46 respectively. The cyclopalladate **3a** has also been characterized by single crystal X-ray crystallography (see Supporting information for details).

The reaction between and 2'-alkylsulfinylphenylazo-4-methoxy-1-naphthalene (HL3' and HL4', Scheme 1) also led to the formation of isomeric cyclopalladates (**3a'** and **3b'**) and (**4a'** and **4b'**). The two sets of isomers, viz. (**3a'** and **4a'**) and (**3b'** and **4b'**) of distinctly different colors, viz. indigo blue and reddish pink respectively (Scheme 3) are isolated by preparative thin layer chromatography on silica. Preliminary analyses indicated them to be isomers with the general formula [Pd^{II}(L)Cl]. However, in order to ascertain the exact binding mode of the terdentate substrates in these two sets of complexes, X-ray crystallographic analysis of the representative members from each group has been undertaken.

The ORTEP diagram of the cyclopalladate (**4a'**) is displayed in Fig. 1 with atom-numbering scheme. The selected set of relevant bond parameters and crystal information data and have been listed in Table 1 and Table S2 (Supporting information). In the cyclopalladate **4a'**, palladium(II) center is bonded to C2 of the azonaphthyl fragment, N2 of the diazo group and S1 at the 2'-position of the phenyl fragment.

Therefore, 2'-benzylsulfinylphenylazo-4-methoxy-1-naphthalene binds palladium(II) as a monoanionic terdentate [C, N, S] ligand forming two five membered chelate rings with 'bite angles' 84.69(8) (N2-Pd1-S1) and 79.24(13) (N2-Pd1-C2). The C, N, S donor set, palladium(II) center and the chloride ion constitute almost a planar geometry. The Pd-S, Pd-C, Pd-N bond distances are normal¹².

Single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction could not be obtained for the pink *peri*-isomers. Eventually, using 2'-ethylsulfinylphenylazo-4-methoxy-1-naphthalene as the diazene substrate, suitable single crystals of the *peri*-iso-

Scheme 3. Isolation of the isomeric cyclopalladates.

Fig. 1. ORTEP plot of the cyclopalladate **4a'** with atom-numbering scheme. All atoms are represented by their 50% probability ellipsoids.

Table 1. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) for the complex (**4a'**)

Bond lengths (Å)		Bond angles (°)	
Pd(1)-N(2)	1.976(3)	N(2)-Pd(1)-C(2)	79.24(13)
Pd(1)-C(2)	1.995(3)	N(2)-Pd(1)-Cl(1)	174.89(8)
Pd(1)-Cl(1)	2.2939(11)	C(2)-Pd(1)-Cl(1)	97.48(11)
Pd(1)-S(1)	2.3499(9)	N(2)-Pd(1)-S(1)	84.69(8)
N(2)-N(1)	1.287(4)	C(2)-Pd(1)-S(1)	63.62(11)
N(1)-C(1)	1.364(5)	Cl(1)-Pd(1)-S(1)	98.33(4)
N(2)-C(12)	1.409(4)		
S(1)-O(2)	1.475(2)		

mer is obtained. The ORTEP diagram of the cyclopalladate (**4b-Et'**) has been shown in Fig. 2. The crystal data confirms the C8(naphthyl)-H bond activation by palladium(II). The crystal information data together and a relevant set of geometric parameters has been tabulated in Table 2 and Table S2 respectively. The palladium(II) center in **4b-Et'** is found to be bonded to C8 (*peri* position of 1-azonaphthyl fragment), N1 of diazo group, S1 of the sulfinyl function and Cl1 thereby providing a quasi-ideal square-planar arrangement around palladium(II). The square planar coordination sphere around the palladium-center of the *peri*-palladated compound (**4b-Et'**) shows coordination angles that are closer to the ideal value of 90°. The 'bite angle' at palladium center of C(8)-Pd(1)-N(2) in (**4b-Et'**) is 91.76(6)°, which is remarkably higher

Fig. 2. ORTEP plot of the cyclopalladate **4b-Et'** with atom-numbering scheme. All atoms are represented by their 50% probability ellipsoids.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) for the complex (**4b-Et'**)

Bond lengths (Å)		Bond angles (°)	
Pd(1)-C(8)	2.008(2)	C(8)-Pd(1)-N(2)	91.76(8)
Pd(1)-N(2)	2.0110(18)	C(8)-Pd(1)-S(02)	176.70(6)
Pd(1)-S(02)	2.3060(6)	N(2)-Pd(1)-S(02)	86.19(5)
Pd(1)-Cl(1)	2.3335(6)	C(8)-Pd(1)-Cl(1)	96.05(6)
N(2)-N(1)	1.269(3)	N(2)-Pd(1)-Cl(1)	169.67(6)
N(2)-C(12)	1.464(3)	S(02)-Pd(1)-Cl(1)	86.31(2)
N(1)-C(1)	1.369(3)		
S(02)-O(2)	1.4798(17)		

than 79.24(13)° found in the *ortho*-palladated complex. Herein, we take into consideration that the alkyl moiety attached to the S atom has no significant role to play in the binding process to the palladium center. The six membered diaza palladacycle has a rather distorted hexagonal geometry with all other angles wider than 120° except for the 'bite' angle at the palladium center which indicates clearly the geometrical constraints exerted by the palladium(II) ion. Further, it is quite unusual that palladium(II) activates the *peri* C(8)-H bond of the azonaphthyl fragment forming a six membered palladacycles with coordination of the palladium center to the more distant azo N atom i.e. N(2)

Thus the indigo blue and reddish pink products have been identified unambiguously as the *ortho*-palladate and *peri*-palladate respectively. Both the isomeric cyclopalladates contain five-membered carbopalladacycle. However, the [N,S] chelate ring is five-membered in the *ortho*-isomer and six-membered in *peri*-isomer.

Tuning the selectivity of C(naphthyl)-H bond activation :

Addition of acids or bases in the reaction media has been found to have an interesting effect on the yield and selectivity of the cyclopalladation reactions. Addition of a few drops of NEt_3 in the methanolic reaction mixture of HL and $[\text{PdCl}_4]^{2-}$ resulted in the formation of the indigo blue cyclopalladates in appreciable yield (*ca.* 60–65%) with a trace amount of the *peri*-isomer (0–3%). When the same reaction is carried out with a few drops of acetic acid, the colour of the reaction mixture slowly turned to red resulting in the formation of the *peri*-isomers in high yields of about 55%. However, negligible amount of formation of (**1a-5a**) with 0–4% yields have also been observed.

It is generally accepted that cyclopalladation is initiated by coordination of a heteroatom to the metal, which is followed by ligand dissociation from the square planar species giving rise to highly reactive intermediate which activates a C-H bond in kinetically controlled electrophilic step with a marked preference for the formation a five-membered palladacycle¹³. In the present case, it is reasonable to believe that due to the ‘softness’ of diazene (-N=N-) and the auxiliary groups, formation of the five-membered [N,S] chelate is likely to occur. The step is followed by [C,N] metallation ultimately forming five-membered (in *ortho*-isomers) and six-membered (in *peri*-isomers) carbopalladacycle. The observed role of base in the cyclopalladation of the diazene substrates can also be appreciated following this mechanistic scenario. The cyclometallation process is associated with a decrease in pH, and therefore addition of base should facilitate carbon-metal bond formation and increase the rate of reaction, as has been found in the present case. Exclusive formation of the *ortho*-palladate (C2-H activation) under basic condition can be explained in terms of the tendency of palladium (and other platinum group metals’) to form five-membered metallacycles over six-membered ones. However, formation of the *peri*-palladates under acidic condition as the major products is not completely clear to us. The research group Professor A. J. Klaus *et al.* thoroughly studied the cyclopalladation of 1,1'-azonaphthalene and showed that the *peri*-palladate having a six-membered metallacycle is the kinetically controlled product whereas the *ortho*-palladate with a five-membered metallacycle is

the thermodynamically favoured product^{13a}. The *peri*-complex was converted completely into the *ortho*-isomer under specific reaction condition. Investigation is underway to draw a conclusive mechanistic pathway of C-H bond activation for these cyclopalladates.

Photochemical studies :

A number of azo-conjugated metal complexes are known to exhibit interesting properties upon light irradiation and are utilized in the area of photon-mode high-density information storage¹⁴. Diazene derivatives are also known for their ability to undergo light-induced or thermal *Z/E* isomerization¹⁵.

Isolation of isomeric cyclopalladates in the present case encouraged us to explore their reactivity, particularly with respect to their thermal or photo-induced interconversion. It is known that the *peri*-hydrogen in naphthyl moiety is more easily removed than the *ortho*-hydrogen atoms¹⁶. Thus, the *peri*-palladates (**3b**, **4b**, **3b'** and **4b'**) having six-membered metallacycles are regarded as the kinetically controlled products. In contrast, the thermodynamically controlled products are the *ortho*-isomers containing five-membered carbopalladacycles (**3a**, **4a**, **3a'** and **4a'**).

Initially, attempts have been made to convert the kinetically controlled *peri*-palladates into the *ortho*-palladates thermally. However, even after refluxing the *peri*-palladates in boiling xylene for a prolonged period, the desired *ortho*-products could not be obtained. Driven by ability of diazene derivatives to undergo photo-induced *cis-trans* isomerism, the photochemical transformation of *peri*-palladates into the corresponding *ortho*-palladates has been studied in presence of sunlight and also using tungsten lamp as a source. Upon exposure to sunlight or tungsten lamp, the characteristic absorption band at 532 nm of the pink coloured *peri*-palladate has been found to decay gradually. Appearance of a new absorption band at 615 nm indicates the generation of the *ortho*-palladates with an isobestic point at ~ 547 nm. The electronic spectral changes obtained in case the cyclopalladate **3b'** are shown in Fig. 4 as a representative case. The process has been found to be completed in about 30–35 days resulting in a blue solution (Fig. 4). Finally, the *ortho*-isomers have been isolated by preparative thin layer chromatography on silica and are given in Table S3 (Supporting information).

Fig. 3. Photochemical transformation from **3b'** to **3a'** in dichloromethane.

Fig. 4. Conversion of the *peri*-palladate (**3b'**) into the *ortho*-palladate (**3a'**) in dichloromethane upon exposure to sunlight.

The photochemical transformation has been found to be solvent dependent and has been observed only in dichloromethane or chloroform. No photochemical isomerization was detected in solvents like benzene, acetonitrile, hexane or toluene.

Conclusion

In the present study, we have investigated and how C(naphthyl)-H bonds present in a group of substrates, alkylthioazonaphthalenes and alkylsulfinylazonaphthalenes, can be selectively activated by palladium(II) at room temperature. Regioselective activation of C2(naphthyl)-H and C8(naphthyl)-H bonds have been achieved by palladium(II) using diazene group at C1 acting as the primary donor and thioether or the sulfinyl being the auxiliary donor. The isolation of *ortho* (C2-Pd) and *peri* (C8-Pd) cyclopalladates with five and six membered chelate sys-

tems respectively has been realized. Acidic and basic additives have been found to play a major role in determining the position of C(naphthyl)-H bond activation. The regioselective activation of C2(naphthyl)-H bond by palladium(II) has been realized by adding a few drops of triethylamine, whereas the activation of C8(naphthyl)-H bond by palladium(II) has been achieved by addition of few drops of glacial acetic acid. In presence of sun light the cyclometallates containing C(8)-Pd bond is slowly converted into its isomer having C(2)-Pd bond in dichloromethane or chloroform.

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